

Cyber Security Framework for Enterprise System Development: Enhancing Domain Security Through ESM

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1.0 ABSTRACT

Securing the DoD information network is a tremendous task due to its size, access locations and the amount of network intrusion attempts on a daily basis. This analysis investigates methods/architecture options to deliver capabilities for secure information sharing environment. Crypto-binding and intelligent access controls are basic requirements for secure information sharing in a net-centric environment. We introduce many of the new technology components to secure the enterprise. The cooperative mission requirements lead to developing automatic data discovery and data stewards granting access to Cross Domain (CD) data repositories or live streaming data. Multiple architecture models are investigated to determine best-of-breed approaches including SOA and Private/Public Clouds. The goal is to familiarize the audience with a selection of common approaches and latest technologies that are instrumental to developing the framework of ESM.

2.0 INTRODUCTION

One of the most recent policy shifts in the DoD and other federal agencies dealing with access and distribution of information has shifted from a need to know paradigm to a need to share paradigm. The shift in policy requires many changes in architecting and developing systems and their security infrastructure to enable interoperability and secure access through common standards, methodologies and technologies that allow us to carefully balance the ability to protect information and the ability to share that information with those who need it most. Traditionally, information owners and stewards had offered limited access to critical data to a limited set of trusted users that have the need and the trust of the Enterprise to access and transfer data to their systems. Increasing dependencies on international partners and blurring of the lines between operational and administrative functions on the network led to new ways to tag and classify information. Additionally, the vast improvements of technologies that allow the warrior in harm's way access to an unprecedented level of tactical and operational information have converged to illustrate the inadequacy of our traditional access management paradigms.[1] Additionally, the U.S. Department of Homeland Security (DHS) has launched Virtual USA (vUSA), a voluntary, practitioner-driven, and federally sponsored initiative focused on cross-jurisdictional information sharing and collaboration among homeland security.[2] This paper proposes a 12-step framework that will allow Enterprise managers to define their boundaries and enable the Enterprise to dynamically adjust to changing

mission needs and requirements. The Framework starts with an initial capability assessment and then moves through the lifecycle of development with security management inserted throughout the process. The unique aspect of this framework centers on agility through continuously re-prioritizing capabilities as dictated by the stakeholders/mission owners. The incremental build plans, as outlined in the framework, allow for this agile environment in order to achieve success and physically deliver mission capability early and often.

3.0 CYBER SECURITY AND ENTERPRISE INFORMATION SHARING

The reason we need this ESM Framework centers on our constantly changing landscape of cyber threat, security and the need to share appropriate information. Since the Enterprise includes all people and assets and information at different sensitivity and restriction levels and users have different credentials and roles that entitle them to access these information types, there will be a need to build cross security domain capabilities. These capabilities vary in complexity and capability based on needs and implanted technologies. Those responsible for combating terrorism must have access to timely and accurate information regarding those who want to initiate an attack on, their plans and activities, and the targets that they intend to attack. That information guides our efforts to identify rapidly both immediate and long-term threats; Identify persons involved in terrorism-related activities; and Implement information-driven and risk-based detection, prevention, deterrence, response, protection, and emergency management efforts. The Strategy is founded on the core principles and understandings shown in Figure 1.

3.1 Bounding the Enterprise

One of the biggest challenges with creating the initial capability assessment for the framework is to identify the boundaries. The Enterprise in our description includes the People, Process, Governance, Data, Information systems, Communication Systems, and all infrastructures related to a common mission or organization. The Enterprise can be composed of loosely or tightly coupled systems and process. This definition leads us to conclude that the boundaries of the enterprise tend to be fuzzy, as there is continuous change in assets and the capabilities as missions are added and changed, and as new organizations join the enterprise due to acquisitions and partnerships.

The Enterprise itself can have multiple levels of sensitive information to be shared between authorized users and protected from being seen or corrupted by internal and

external entities that are not authorized to access such information. Within the Department of Defense (DoD), there are four main classifications, Unclassified, Confidential, Secret, and Top Secret. Within these classifications, there are additional markings that determines who can access these data sets, including countries and agencies that can view data to enable allies and coalition forces to work together in executing the mission.

Figure 1 Foundations of the National Strategy for Information Sharing [3]

The process of automating information sharing requires that all data be tagged with the source, date, time, sensitivity level, and criteria on sharing. Moreover, these tags need to be securely attached to the data itself and authenticated to the producer. Privilege Management provides the means to make information visible and accessible. The use of advanced access control models like Policy-Based, Attribute-Based, and Risk-Adaptive and the implementation of Service Oriented Architectures (SOA) using standards-based authentication, assertion, and authorization methods will provide the community an unprecedented ability to employ fine-grained access control. [4]

3.2 Concepts of Cross Domain Enterprise Services

Any reference to cyber implies a cross domain component, so the insertion of IA throughout the framework will need to consider the cross domain aspects. Based on our initial description, the Enterprise can be composed on information systems containing multiple levels of security and sensitivity. The most primitive form of security Cross Domain (CD) is using information systems that are designated to a single security level, and have no automated connection between these systems. Data transfer is done manually, by an operator/manager from a single entry point after performing manual checks. The next step included varying level of automated point-to-point (P2P) connections between information systems where information is allowed to propagate between two domains under the accepted rules and governance. The ideal approach is utilizing Enterprise services. Enterprise CD Services are a method by which services are provided in a centralized approach to the subscribers. The services are provided to the subscribers in a manner that is consistent with a pre determined approach governed by a service level agreement that includes type, capacity and priority of services. The process of sharing information between systems of different security levels is

done securely through a cross domain device. These devices are one of three types, Access, Transfer, and Multi Level. Figure 2 shows possible architectures of CD services.

Figure 2 Migrating from Consolidated CD to Integrated CD Services [5]

3.3 Security of Information Sharing

The new CD services are designed to allow for the maximum sharing of information between domains while ensuring that all data is protected to the designated level. The data should be protected while on the move or while on the halt, therefore the routing of such data over the communication links must be of highest consideration. These issues will be of higher importance when working with Virtualized and Cloud computing as described in section 5.0 of this paper. There is a certain increase in the risk we take when we implement Information Sharing in such a wide state where discovery and subscriptions are automated based on predetermined user privileges; however, the potential rewards are overwhelmingly positive and allow the enterprise to track changes in the environment and react in real time to react and take protective measures.

3.4 User Experience

To enable successful delivery of capability early and often, the concept of incremental builds is an important part of the ESM Framework as well as the development of operational threat scenarios. The Users or stakeholders play an important role in defining and validating these cyber capabilities. Users of Multi-Level Security information have few options on how attain that capability. The most common way used today is to purchase a device that provides CD through P2P services between two security domains. In general, low to high is mostly automated and the High to low utilizes human reviewer. As we start upgrading CD capabilities to consolidated and then integrated services, the users should start associating the capability with the service provider and not the physical device. This will prove to be a revolutionary approach analogous to providing converged voice, video, and data over the same data links. Many of the advantages that users will see are the inherent redundancy and increased utilization of native IP queuing algorithms.

3.5 Service Provider View

The potential steps that need to be taken into consideration in migrating to an Enterprise service view is to develop and certify essential technologies that include Remote Management of CD assets, Virtual CD Services and Cloud computing among others. Adhering to an ESM Framework that allows for these technologies is critical to the implementation of these cyber capabilities. There also has to be a universally acceptable way for data tagging and meta-data formatting. There also are some obvious advantages from consolidating the services and a promise of more advantages of the integrated Enterprise capabilities.

3.6 Development Roadmap

The road to a fully automated information sharing across the Enterprise and to external entities that might be outside the predefined security domains requires an incremental buildup of technologies, cultures, governance, and training of users and managers. Although many of our systems can interoperate and share data at some level, we need to allow automated search, discovery and dynamic application of policies to accommodate for changing threats, policies and environmental conditions. We also would need to track data; who has accessed, and/or modified it in order for decision makers to confidently assess the situation, share data, and make decisions. Figure 3 shows how the notional steps to enable a fully automated Information Sharing Environment (ISE) through a services-enabled CD Enterprise.

It is obvious that the ISE being developed by many organizations today would not reach its intended capabilities without having a CD Enterprise Services (CDES) that can provide all the capabilities needed for a Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) to succeed. Moreover, as we move forward to cloud architecture, we need to assess the future needs of a collaborative Enterprise that depends on the Cloud structure to process information and share data

The transformation from a centralized, sequential thinking to a distributed, parallel information sharing and dynamic collaboration approach requires a fundamental shift in the way systems are built. Specifically, it lends itself to a SOA on a ubiquitous network transporting large data sets on demand. [6]

4.0 NOTABLE ESM SERVICES

Enterprise Security Management (ESM) framework must include protecting all past, current and future data, sources and methods as well as all authorized users' identity. This task also includes ensuring that the data is reliable and available in time to legitimate users. Methods of crypto-binding the data with metadata and sources, which will be discussed in the technology trends section, in addition to tracking the users that have accessed compromised data are basic requirements for secure information sharing in a network centric environment. This new system of systems needs to have automatic data discovery and enable data stewards to grant access to authenticated users. Multiple

architecture models need further investigation to determine best of breed approach including SOA and Private/Public Clouds that support mission needs while ensuring the needed security level.

Figure 3 Notional Steps of building ISE with CDES

4.1 Access Control Features of ESM

To enable a next generation ESM construct we need to develop the baseline technologies that support Credential and Identity Management to ensure the proper Privileges are granted. The proposed ESM Framework provides for these conditions. Data access is granted based on identifying the data including Attributes and Metadata and then it is distributed to authorized users based on an updated Digital Policy. The current ESM approach assumes the use of a method of access control including Role Based, Authorization Based, Attribute Bases Access Control (RBAC, ABAC, and ZBAC, etc.). Cryptographic Key Management plays an important role in protecting data at-halt and data at-the-move and therefore is required in any architecture. IA Audit and Configuration Management are also essential elements of managing security. Some technologies here are disruptive technologies that could revolutionize enterprise security. For example, an identity management (ID mgmt) system provides the necessary processes and infrastructure to allow users to easily create and manage their online identity allowing them to login from anywhere to applications on the network. Moreover, the ID mgmt systems allow applications to apply appropriate rules and policies to control user access and privileges. Secure access control would not be possible unless we know with certainty the identity, role, and other key attributes of any user who logs in, and to maintain records of this information. The Privilege management system allows privileges to be granted and removed when roles change, preventing unauthorized access to systems, while continuously executing resources tracking. Additionally, the vision going forward is to deploy a flexible and adaptive privilege management capability operating in near-real time to create

and enforce risk-calculated access decisions that ensure the enterprise supports the intent of mission commanders. [7]

4.2 Cross Domain Services

The service provider can provide CD services in one of two ways: 1) provide connectivity to a guard via static entry/exit point or 2) provide a subscription to the enterprise capability that is provided over a service bus. The use of load balancing systems on the entry/exit points can be employed to attempt and automate the systems to handle demand surges by individual customers as the case with employing the Single Point Access (SPA) by DISA.

4.3 Trusted Operating Systems and Supporting Hardware Architectures

Key to ESM is the undercarriage or foundational infrastructure, which includes the Operating System (OS) and the Hardware in which it runs. Secure OS have been the subject of much research and various implementations for many years. The basic tenets put forth for any OS to be secure are: *Non-bypassable, Evaluatable, Always invoked and Tamper-proof.* One method of protecting critical information systems is to have the Core of Secure Operating System run from a read-only memory partition, making it immune to infections from malicious threats, such as viruses and malware.

The separation of system services from the Kernel and architecting multiple isolated types of system services as shown in Figure 4 allows them to be evaluated at the highest required security level. In this way, it is possible for the system to support applications of mixed security levels since the security policies are at the highest level in the system and can allow or deny communication between differing levels of security. This is referred to as Multi Level Security is needed by DoD for their future systems. A true MLS will allow the DoD the ability to have soldiers in the field use systems that are capable of accessing information varying in sensitivity level and ensuring that data will not accidentally be shared with personnel who are not cleared to the appropriate level. This eliminates the need for all the embedded computers in a system to run system high. [8]

5.0 TECHNOLOGY TRENDS THAT ENABLE ESM

The development of a framework for ESM assumes a persistent need for the following:

5.1 Crypto Binding of Meta-Data

The function crypto-binding is to provide multiple levels of security tagged data from multiple domains with assurance that the information was not tampered with during the delivery process. The goal is to develop a MLS information flow utilizing trusted metadata that provides security and pedigree assurance. Analysis of Security trends shows that metadata is becoming increasingly important as a means for describing information content and formats so as to facilitate

access to, and improve the processing of that content. In the context of multiple-layer security devices the integrity of metadata is fundamental to overall system integrity since the metadata typically contains the information regarding classification level, producer, data steward, collection location, time/date and the security mechanisms that have been applied to the content. The next step is to develop an object-based information repository accessible across multiple security domains wherein each object's metadata homogeneously describes that object's security status accurately, fully, and securely. There should be a commonly accepted standard-compliant mechanism for embedding security information in an object's metadata. This information should include not only the security classification of the object, but also its pedigree. This history would describe the who/what/when of all access and processing to which the object has been subjected from its inception.

Figure 4 Top-level diagram of the separation kernel.

5.2 Secure Remote Management

Implementation of Information Sharing has dramatically increased demand for secure remote access to multiple IT operations within the enterprise or large government entities. Additionally, when working with the virtualized services, we tend to create a need for more remote infrastructures. The increasingly mobile work and warfighter force led system administrators to increase the role of remotely managed service as service provider instead of local management of assets. The increase of Configuration Control, consistent patching, and reduced administrative costs comes with a price of perceived lower security because of the increased access to the systems control mechanisms. This situation needs to be mitigated by stronger access controls mechanisms, increased monitoring, increased auditing and more passive and positive control over the assets. Many organization and research facilities are developing highly secure remote management methods and products to allow system administrators control over local, virtualized and shared assets in serving the organization's mission.

5.3 Services Based Architecture

For standard Web services using SOAP, Security has achieved critical mass as a foundational standard. On the other hand, advanced SOA security involving federation among partners, non-repudiation, and propagation of user identities across multiple layers of service implementations is in its early days. To navigate the path from what's practical

today to the future of advanced SOA security; establish an iterative design process for evolving your SOA security architecture that considers your current and future security requirements, emerging industry specifications, overlaps in product functionality for SOA security, and possibilities for custom security integration. As a baseline for designing SOA security, the simplest way to secure SOA requests and responses is to place them within a virtual private network (VPN). The most common method for external SOA security is two-way Secure Sockets Layer (SSL). Although VPNs are relatively easy to establish, VPN-based SOA security is coarse-grained and offers no ability to support advanced functions such as: propagation of user identity across multiple layers of service implementations; coordination and federation among multiple security domains; and strict non-repudiation. Also ongoing management of certificates can be an administrative burden. Even with the emerging features of application servers and SOA specialty products, simple SOA security solutions can be compelling. [9]

5.4 Private/Public Clouds

Enterprise strategists have shown strong interest in cloud computing. A recent definition of cloud computing shows a shift towards delivering dynamically scalable IT resources as services over the Internet. These services typically share some key attributes, such as elasticity, resource sharing, multi-tenancy, self-service, and pay per use. The main types of survives are a public and private cloud. Private clouds host cloud services in the enterprise's own data centers; while external service providers provide public clouds service. Security of cloud computing is the biggest concern of today's Enterprise. Information Security, isolation, and multi-tenancy are key requirements of any cloud. Even though multi-tenancy is built into every public cloud, it will take some time before enterprises are comfortable trusting cloud provider security and placing sensitive corporate data on the public cloud. The cloud are based on incorporating virtualization and management technologies that abstract away the physical infrastructure and present to the application layer virtual computing servers, virtual storage, and virtual networking. The Enterprise can concurrently include private, public and hybrid cloud structure to process and store varying levels of sensitive information. [10]

6.0 THE PROPOSED ESM FRAMEWORK

It is envisioned that the currently distributed P2P services will move into a collaborative domain where federated Enterprise services will be available to service the Enterprise. CD services along with other security services will enable ESM to be realized through a framework that can be implemented in a straightforward manner. This will also allow the Tactical users to connect securely to the enterprise to utilize these services, along with a method for the tactical users to individual trusted P2P services to manage Cross Domain when access to the Enterprise is not possible or not recommended for operational reasons. Additional capabilities will need to be added in the future including

automated discovery and publish and subscribe to enable better sharing of data as soon as it becomes available. Again, implementing this ESM Framework will enable dynamic reconfiguration as mission needs dictate. Figure 5 shows the maturity curve of implementing a framework over time. The proposed 12-step Framework for implementing ESM is presented as it is currently being piloted in various organizations within the DoD.

1. Initial Capability Assessment. This effort involves the analysis of current capabilities through the identification of assets and knowledge based systems. This assessment provides the "As Is" integrated architecture that facilitates secure information exchange between geographically connected and disjoint units.
2. Develop Operational Scenarios for Defensive and Offensive ESM based on threat level and adversary capabilities. This effort entails working with the warfighter and leadership to understand the current and future plans of utilizing information technology to fight the cyber war in conjunction with the traditional activities. This is a continuous effort that should take the enterprise from being reactive to threats to adaptive and dynamic as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5 Enterprise Security Services Maturity Curve

3. Develop/update the ESM Requirements. The requirements development effort should be delivered in multiple views. The first view addresses the operational capabilities involving ESM in cross domain. The second view addresses the technical capabilities that focus on the type, frequency, persistence, Quality and the location of service. The third view addresses System/component requirements.
4. Validate Requirements. This stage is designed to go back and get feedback from the stakeholder leadership and the warfighting units to ensure that the draft requirements meet the needs and are broad enough to accommodate most of the potential future plans.
5. Develop a Capability Gap Analysis. The development of gap analysis starts with in-depth analysis of current policy and technology. The gaps are broken down Technology Gaps and Policy Gaps to ensure proper mitigation methods.

6. Prioritize Operational Needs in light of Gaps and Funding. After thorough review of the gaps, and the roadmap objectives, the operational needs and the requirements are prioritized.
7. Develop a high Level Architecture. The next step is to develop architecture to enable data sharing between partners and prohibit the adversaries from gaining access to the data at-rest or at-the-move. The proposed architecture needs to be flexible to accommodate changes of plans, adoption of new policies and the development of new disruptive technologies for offensive or defensive missions. This architecture needs to be verified via prototyping, modeling and simulation and subjected to a red team's analysis.
8. Develop Incremental build plans. Once the capabilities are prioritized and the architecture is adopted, we start developing an incremental build plan that accommodates the user needs in the required timeframe.
9. Manage the Development. The effort involves the development of a core leadership team that is well trained to deliver offensive and defensive capabilities in an organized manner. Initially, there is a push to develop a strategy, goals, objectives, and organizational roadmap. The following deliverable proved to be the highest priority: Fiscal; Personnel; Timeline; and Equipment.
10. Monitor the Technology Trends and Potential Adversary Approaches. There is a continuous need to monitor technology trends and adversary's adoption of these technologies. This is essential for interoperability and attacking enemies as described in section 5.
11. Continually adjust the capability Priorities and promising technologies. As the theater of operation changes and the political environment progresses, there is a need for periodic re-assessment of requirements, capabilities and updating the architectures. As these changes happen, the team reassesses the priorities and changes them to accommodate emerging threats.
12. Work with Stakeholders including Services and Agencies to ensure interoperability and leveraging their investments. This role is to continuously work with all the Services and Agencies to build common capabilities utilizing pre-certified tools.

7.0 SUMMARY

To enable a next-generation ESM construct we need to develop the baseline technologies and a framework by which we can continually assess, at an Enterprise level, how we manage security components from the physical layer through the application layer. CD services are designed to allow for the maximum sharing of information between domains while ensuring that all data is protected to the designated level. The data should be protected while on the move or while on the halt, therefore the routing of such data over the communication links must be of highest consideration. Some of the more mature aspects of Enterprise Security must be leveraged particularly ones that support Credential

and Identity Management to ensure the proper Privileges are granted, monitored and audited. Data access is granted based on identifying the data including Attributes and Metadata and then it is distributed to authorized users based on an updated Digital Policy. Secure access control would not be possible unless we know with certainty the identity, role, and other key attributes of any user who logs in, and to maintain records of this information. The pilots currently underway will flesh out the specific details of how we can successfully implement the framework so that it can be internally optimized. Supporting the tenets of information sharing and securing the Enterprise, we must conform to an ideology that enables us to share through a protected means and a process that allows us to dynamically adjust to accommodate National Security Strategy. The framework presented takes advantage of decades of system development techniques and leverages the presented security methods and technologies to arrive at a secure and flexible architecture for the enterprise.

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